

Figure 2. Comparison of metabolite data of allopolloid species *N. rustica* (A), *N. tabacum* (B) and *N. benthamiana* (C) to descendants of their diploid progenitors. Data from Table S2 was represented as average values of six biological replicates in a heatmap with hierarchical clustering of *Nicotiana* species and metabolites.

